

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF ECOLOGICAL TERRITORIAL ORGANIZATION OF THE CITY

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Abstract: In the article the main principles of the territorial organization of urban planning on an urban-ecological basis are studied and characterized.

Key words: principles, urboecology, urbanization, landscape design, urban architecture, hierarchical systems, buffer zones.

In urban planning, ecological principles are measured by various objects in the urban area, the structure of the economic infrastructure, natural features of the area, and its suitability and proportionality for constructions. The stability of the ecological balance in the urban area is directly related to the density of the population in the urban area, the purpose of using the area, and the movement of production. Urboecologically, one of the important factors that make up an urban area is related to the population and its density load on the urban area. In determining the ecologically critical limit of the population, various indicators are used as a basis, and the most important of them are the hygienic criteria and the presence of various institutions that satisfy the needs of the population. In the experience of the countries of the world, the critical limits of the population indicators of the city have been defined differently. For example, in Germany, the critical limit of population density in urban areas is set from 100 to 1500 people per 1 km².

Among the total area occupied by cities, 28% of the city area is allocated for transport communications, 42% for agricultural areas, recreation areas, 30% for

water areas, forests and other lands. According to American urban planning and urbanization experts, urbanized areas, agricultural areas and open spaces should be in the ratio 1:1:1, and 3 hectares of land per person is defined as the ecological norm. In Poland, according to urban ecological principles, the density in the cores of urban agglomerations can reach 3000-5000 people, for agglomerations 800-2000 people, and for urbanized regions 300-1000 people per 1 km².

The construction of cities uses a lot of natural factors and artificial structures in their landscape design. In the construction of ancient and medieval cities, ornamental plants were formed in the form of trees and bushes, orchards, avenues, and parks. At the same time, construction of natural and artificial reservoirs has been started. For example, the Labi reservoir in Bukhara was built for this purpose. Areas crossed by rivers and streams, shores of lakes and seas have been able to perform particularly important economic and political tasks in urban development. For example: the capital of Hungary is located on both sides of the Danube.

It was formed from the merger of the cities of Buda and Pesht. In the creation of the cities of the Middle East and Central Asia, especially water sources played an important role as a natural resource. Ancient cities such as Pop (Bob), Koson, Uzgen, Ahsikent, Qubba, Ershi, which served as the capital during the medieval statehood of the Fergana Valley, were also built on the banks of rivers and streams. Modern urban planning, urban architecture and landscape design, in addition to the ancient traditional methods of urban planning, widely use comprehensive research in the construction of cities for their modern appearance, durability of buildings, flawless operation of the communication system.

This makes it possible to expand the economic, political, cultural, and administrative capabilities of cities, and to increase the influence of cities at the national level. Recently, the number of multifunctional cities is increasing. Such cities are actively urbanizing compared to other cities and changing their appearance very quickly. Urbo-ecological organization of urban planning should be based on the landscape characteristics and resource potential of the place chosen for cities.

This principle has been followed in all periods of historical development. A random situation or process was not the basis for the construction of cities. Many cities are located in ecotopic geographical settings. It is known that in urban planning, the mutual proportion of natural and artificial objects should be taken into account. First of all, the natural landscape factor determines the urban space, its plan, and architecture. Relief is one of the main factors in the construction of cities, and contrast is prominent in landscape design. For example, the city of Moscow is built on 7 large hills and has multi-level architecture. In our republic, cities such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Namangan, Andijan were also built on the basis of multi-level architecture.

The most important aspect of modern urbanism is the stabilization of landscape-urban relations by creating hierarchical systems of cities, ensuring the balance of natural and artificial objects. The following hierarchical levels are distinguished in the landscape of cities: 1. macro level: urban agglomeration, urbanized district, territorial industrial complex; 2. mesolevel: selective landscape, industrial landscape, agrolandscape; 3. micro level: courtyard, sports ground, pedestrian zone. Such a hierarchical level of the urban landscape is highly urbanized in our republic. It was formed in many cities such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Navoi, Ferghana, Almalyk, Akhangaran. In these cities, together with agglomerations, urbanized areas, industrial complexes, selected landscapes, agglomerations, residential areas, sports fields are considered components of the urban landscape. Most of the cities located in the territory of our republic correspond to the meso-level hierarchy. The main characteristic of this level is the average level of urbanization, the optimality of the city area, the proportional location of residential areas, industrial facilities and agglomeration. Industrial enterprises are located at a distance of at least 4-5 km from residential quarters.

Sanitary protection zones, agro-landscapes form intermediate buffer zones. Anthropogenic pressure will not be high in such cities. When agro-industrial facilities are located 5-6 km away from populated areas along the direction of air

flow, geochemical analytical fields do not reach populated areas. Organizing the construction of cities on the basis of urbo-ecological principles, ensuring landscape-city balance and stability consists in determining the natural-historical levels that are largely related to the functional development of cities, separating the components of the urban landscape (natural and artificial), optimizing their interactions. This process requires zoning of the city territory, reduction of anthropogenic pressure on the central core of cities, creation of buffer zones, expansion of cities in buffer zones. Ensuring the balance of natural and man-made objects in the landscape of cities, their territorial location stabilizes urbo-ecological situations in cities.

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